

Mapping Anglo-Swiss Travel Writing in the 17th and 18th Century

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As part of the SNSF project SwissBritNet: Swiss-British Cultural Exchange and Knowledge Networks 1600-1780, my PhD project focuses on Anglo-Swiss travel writing in the 17th and 18th centuries. Especially the 17th century has been neglected in Anglo-Swiss research, despite the existence of an intricate network of transcultural exchange and travel at the time (Larminie 2021, 169). The double focus on both British travellers in Switzerland and Swiss travellers in Great Britain will yield insights into reciprocity, points of negotiation and mechanisms of cultural exchange. Since Swiss travellers to Great Britain are under-researched, many of the accounts are manuscripts and neither digitalized nor transcribed. All extant sources, which amount to almost 100 accounts so far, will be catalogued in the SwissBritNet database in collaboration with hallerNet at Bern, and key texts will be made available. Further, the texts will be analysed with the help of software tools such as nodegoat in order to create diachronic geospatial networks and accessible interactive map visualizations as well as social networks. These will track itineraries and offer a point of entry for explorations of transcultural exchange, since maps “can be productive sites of questioning encounter for literary history and criticism” (Eve 2022, 114). Importantly, neither mapping nor travelling are ‘neutral’ in any way: The journeys, encounters and resulting dynamic networks that are visualized on the maps are to be seen as explorations of national and individual identity, given that “there can be no definition of the Self without an Other” (Youngs 2013, 159). Networks and maps are at their core heuristic tools which simplify data and the world into an abstract representation of what the map maker claims as truth (Crampton 2009, 34). In addition to the itineraries, key aspects of the texts are likewise tracked: what are they describing in their accounts of each location, who do they meet, who do they cite, how do they travel? This allows not only for a more in-depth meta-analysis of what travellers do but also reveals the complexities of social encounters and transcultural networks. In the context of our project, one of the open questions is which role travel literature, seen from a diachronic geospatial network point of view, plays in a multi-faceted discourse of Anglo-Swiss relations. I contend that it is a key genre whose study will enhance our understanding of the formation of identity. In my paper, I will present the use of nodegoat for the purposes of tracking the travel accounts with the examples of Thomas Coryate and Thomas Platter, demonstrating the use of geospatial as well as social networks in revealing transcultural exchange.

References

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